

P R E S E N T A T I O N

Svetlana Osokina analyzes the leading linguistic conceptions which study the epistemological function of the language and offers some perspectives of research in this direction. The main perspective of her study is the development of the conception of thesaurus as the language system of knowledge.

This research paper of **Abdul Ghaffar Khan** and **Mohammed Ahmad Alward** deals with the linguistic analysis of Arabic loan words in the present-day Urdu vocabulary. The authors analyzed the morphological aspects of Arabic loan words in Urdu focusing on the inflectional and derivational processes.

Gergana Atanassova Petkova studies the most popular clinical eponyms from the point of view of their formation.

Ioana-Iulia Olaru analyzes the progress in Roman portrait during classical antiquity, without reaching the issue of a footprint that puts Late Antiquity and Christianity on statuary. The author's interest is focused on the artistic development of *ronde bosse* imperial sculpture, on the official propaganda which operated at a maximum level and very directly for this artistic area.

Liliana Bejenaru studies the problem of French appellatives from the perspective of structure, semantic and pragmatic values.

The study of **Luminița Hoartă Cărăușu** brings together several observations which refer to special conditions of holding a TV debate, in a special speech situational context. The author addresses some issues that occurred in a media controlled interaction (a TV debate). The article presents a case study of a night TV debate, whose moderator is Marina Constantinescu and whose guest is Gigi Căciuleanu, choreographer and a famous dancer, coming from a Romanian diaspora.

Gina Măciucă investigates the 'transposition of temporal reference', including: Simple Present for past/future time, Present Progressive for future time, Past Simple/Progressive for present time, Past Perfect Simple/Progressive for hypothetical past, hypothetical Simple Past for future time, and Past Progressive for future time in the past. The author submits to the reader four types of extended structure featuring tempoaspectual blends - with two, three, four and five modal and/or passive and/or lexical auxiliaries - , some of them bona fide ill-conceived lexematic monstrosities.

Stella Gorban analyzes the role of parentheses in the text in order to demonstrate the real functions of these language units. Being analyzed within the sentence, they seem to be easily avoided, replaced without deteriorating the structure of the sentence. Only within the text boundaries parentheses act as important markers of the relations of motivations between parts of the text contributing to text cohesion. They can unite in one communication discourse closely and distantly located blocks of texts, creating an orderly structure of the text, systematizing the ideas in logical chains, introducing more clarity to the information intended by the writer.

The second contribution of **Gina Măciucă** included in the volume is intended to offer a few glimpses of the English Voice, with a major focus in the first section on the mediopassive and the various labels attached to it. Section Two takes the reader to coreferentiality and the vexed problem of English reflexives. It is as late as Section Three that the English Passive finally looms as large as ever. Here three issues are being addressed: the distinct functions of the passive participle - identical in structure to the perfect participle; the role of agent by-phrases, which have been lately promoted from peripheral constituents to active participants in verb complementation; semanticopragmatic conditions accounting for ellipsis of the agent in passive constructions.

The final section features the grammatical device 'promotion to subject' as a semantic rival of the canonical passive, while charting their main diverging contextually-based trends.

Max Graff analyzes the trilogy about Selb by Bernhard Schlink. B. Schlink's touches upon the theme of nationalism in his trilogy, and namely, upon the influence of the past on the present, terrorism and German reunification, the questions of justice and responsibility during the post-war time.

In the article of **Ioana Boghian**, the semiotic approach to the act of naming houses found in 19th-century English novels is meant to reveal the significations of a common cultural practice of the time, particularly belonging to middle-class and wealthy families owning a house/manor/hall: that of attributing names to houses.

Angela Coşciug studies the close contact of French, Spanish, Romanian and Russian reflected in the qualitative and quantitative features of the vowels.

Natalia Banaru analyzes the quantity and the quality of the phonic elements of the hiatus.

Ecaterina Niculcea examines the romantic writers' point of view on the figure of Satan.

Grigore Cantemir investigates the incorrect grammatical forms which have penetrated into current literary and publicistic Romanian texts and which have been „legitimized” by some legislation in force in Republic of Moldova.

Erdal Derinöz explores the usage of metaphors of light and darkness in E. T. A. Hoffmann's short story "Mademoiselle de Scudéri".

In her first article, **Georgiana Elisabeta Panait** investigates the problem of water in terms of intertextuality and symbolism relying on literature and culture.

In her article based on "North Symphony" by Andrey Bely, **Ina Gajeva** explores the principles of pattern prose such as: decreasing the plot role, complex polygenetics of characters and motives and continuous text troping.

Natalia Khalina studies the linguistic features of presidential liberalism in Modern Russia.

In her second article included in this volume, **Georgiana Elisabeta Panait** explores the prosaic vision and poetry in Ion Vinea's works.

Medea Kintsurashvili and **Maya Benidze** study in semiotic terms the island from M. Tournier's novel "Friday or the Limbo of the Pacific", referring essentially to R. Barthes' theory of punctum and praxis, applying its basic principles for the operation of the island as a sign.

Irina Strechii translates some of Grigore Vieru's poems in English.

Luiza Şoşu translates some of Grigore Vieru's and Mihai Eminescu's poems in English.

In the paragraph „Poems and Other Works”, **Georgiana Elisabeta Panait** presents some of her own poems and **Luiza Şoşu** comes with a poem and a tale.